

European coordinated efforts for access and analysis of environmental data: the ENVRI-Hub NEXT approach

Tiziana Ferrari

Director, ESGI Foundation

TLP: WHITE Public

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A Global Challenge

- We live in a **data-rich** but **insight-poor** world
- Environmental **data is fragmented** across thousands of sources, limiting its potential
- The **urgency** of climate change demands
 - FAIR, AI-ready data
 - Advanced computing capacity
 - Truly global collaboration

- ENVRI Community is a collaborative group of **27 European environmental Research Infrastructures** working together to observe and understand the Earth system and its interaction.
- **14 RIs** featured on the **ESFRI Roadmap**
- ENVRI RIs provide **high-quality, open and FAIR in situ data** from the different components of the Earth system from the four domains: Atmosphere, Marine, Ecosystems, Solid Earth.

ACTRIS
AnaEE
ARISE
AQUACOSM

DANUBIUS
DiSSCO
EISCAT_3D
ELIXIR
eLTER

EMBRC
EMPHASIS
EMSO
EPOS
EUFAR

EURO-ARGO
EUROCHAMP 2020
EUROFLEETS
EuroGOOS

HEMERA
IAGOS
ICOS
INTERACT
IS-ENES

JERICO-RI
LifeWatch
SEADATANET
SIOS

What is ENVRI-Hub

- A **single entry point** to Europe's environmental Research Infrastructures
- Built around **Essential Climate Variables** (ECVs) to drive climate and sustainability science
- Seamless **discovery, access, and analysis** across atmosphere, land, ocean and solid Earth
- Designed for **interdisciplinary research** and innovation

United by Science

- **11 Research infrastructures + EGI Federation**
- Covering the whole **Earth system**
- Creating a **global laboratory** without walls
- Ensuring that science serves society and sustainability

- The ENVRI-Hub is the **Competence Centre** for the ENVRI Community
- **Researchers gain easy access to a wealth of environmental data**, enabling faster and more comprehensive interdisciplinary research.
- The platform features **cross RI harmonised discovery, access, single sign-on** through a dedicated instance of Check in an ready-for-cloud applications and services.
- **Cross-RI data analysis workflows** enable the extraction of valuable insights for innovative scientific products.

Federating Compute & Storage

EGI provides large-scale compute, storage & cloud federation

Enabling Predictive Analysis

EGI enables predictive analytics & decision -support systems

Delivering AI Models & Tools

EGI enables AI models and analytical tools to unlock environmental data

Integrating Data via EOOSC

EGI helps to maximise the data value chain through integration with EOOSC

[01]

DEVELOP

Get an interactive development environment (Jupyter Lab or Visual Studio code) to build your model

[02]

TRAIN

Train your model on EU state-of-the-art e-Infrastructures

[03]

SHARE

Publish your model as a reusable asset in our Marketplace

[04]

SERVE

Deploy your model at scale using serverless computing

Credits: AI4EOSC project

ESGI Federation

A collaboration of interoperable and integrated open infrastructures for data-intensive computing, federating a network of **+200** research data centers from **+42 countries** worldwide

- +116,000** users from **+160** countries
- +250** research collaborations supported
- 20** Research Infrastructures partnering in R&D
- 21** Years of history

EGI & Europe's Digital Backbone

EGI Federation: Europe's Largest Federation of Research Data Centers and Cloud Providers

Mission

Empower researchers with advanced computing and data services to solve global challenges

Role in Europe

Trusted digital backbone for science without borders

Community

- Hundreds of national institutes, national e-infrastructures, research infrastructures, and service providers
- +200 Data centers from +42 countries and European organisations, united by Open Science

Global Role

- Extend European leadership to global collaborations
- Enable interoperability and support worldwide scientific challenges

EGI High Throughput Computing Infrastructure

+220 data centers
42 countries

EGI Cloud Compute Sites

EGI Cloud infrastructure

31 federated research clouds from Europe, Asia and Africa

Environment

EISCAT_3D
EMSO-ERIC
EURO-ARGO ERIC
LifeWatch ERIC
EPOS ERIC
SeaDataNet

Health & Food

Euro-BioImaging ERIC
EMPHASIS
EU-OPENSREEN ERIC
INSTRUCT-ERIC

Social & Cultural Innovation

CESSDA ERIC
CLARIN

Physical Sciences & Engineering

CTA
ELI ERIC
HL-LHC
SKAO
European XFEL
KM3Net 2.0

Digital RIs

SoBigData
OPERAS

RIs Engaged Through Projects

ACTRIS ERIC, AnaEE ERIC, Data Terra, EPOS ERIC, eLTER, IAGOS, ICOS ERIC, SeaDataNet, SIOS, EMBRC ERIC, EIRENE RI, IS-ENES, EBRAINS, ECRIN ERIC, METROFOOD-RI, OPERAS, E-RIHS

- ENVRI-Hub = Europe's contribution to global Open Science
- Alignment with
 - **EOSC** – Europe's Open Science Cloud
 - **UN SDGs** – Sustainable Development Goals
 - **Global Open Science Cloud initiative, UNESCO, GEO** – Global science partnerships
- Designed for global access and collaboration

EGI – CNIC MoU

05 September 2025

- 1 Empowering researchers with **AI-ready, interoperable data**

- 2 Accelerating breakthrough on **climate, biodiversity, sustainability**

- 3 Positioning Europe as a **global partner in digital science infrastructures**

- 4 Building an **open, collaborative, sustainable digital ecosystem**

Call to action

Environmental challenges know no borders. Neither should our science.

Let's unite computing, data, and science to safeguard our planet worldwide